

Reducing Distortion in Steganography using Syndrome Trellis Code

Bhavya K S

Department of Electronics and
Communication Engineering, JSS
Academy of Technical Education,
Bengaluru, India

Deepika H V

Department of Electronics and
Communication Engineering, JSS
Academy of Technical Education,
Bengaluru, India

Harshavardhini V

Patil

Department of Electronics and
Communication Engineering, JSS
Academy of Technical Education,
Bengaluru, India

Yeswanth Reddy K

Department of Electronics and
Communication Engineering, JSS
Academy of Technical Education,
Bengaluru, India

Latha B N

Assistant Professor, Dept. of ECE,
JSSATE, Bengaluru, India

Dr. Sathish Shet K

Assistant Professor, Dept. of ECE,
JSSATE, Bengaluru, India

Abstract: *Data protection is one of the most daunting issues facing the technology world today. Numerous schemes have been proposed over the last decade to protect the transmission of confidential data over the public network (Internet). Steganography, along with cryptography, can be one of the best ways to solve this problem. The word stego is the Greek word "Secret." Steganography is the process of embedding a hidden message to an image. Essentially, distortion occurs as pixel length increases, as distortion increases hackers can easily target the computer and can easily view the information contained in the image. The non-binary embedding scheme by syndrome-trellis codes is used here to reduce the distortion. The role of the Trellis Syndrome Code in steganography is to assign a scalar to any possible value of a stego element representing the distortion of an embedding shift by replacing that value with the cover element. The entire distortion is assumed to be a portion of the pre-element distortions.*

Keywords: *Steganography; Syndrome Trellis Code; Distortion*

I. INTRODUCTION

Web users are expected to store, receive, or send information periodically. The most regular way of doing the process is to transform the knowledge into another form. Only those who know how to restore it to its original content will understand the data resulting therefrom.

This method is called as encoding or encryption. One of the big drawbacks of encoding is that it doesn't disguise information existence. Although the data encoded is illegible. It still exists in data form. If adequate time is granted, the data can eventually be decrypted by anyone.

This can be solved by steganography. Steganography is the art and science of concealing knowledge, and a steganographic scheme blends confidential material into unremarkable cover media in order to avoid raising the suspicion of an eavesdropper. People used secret tattoos or translucent tin beforehand for the steganographic data transmission. The computer and network technologies provide the steganography system with easy-to-use communication networks.

In essence, the method of information hiding begins with a steganographic approach by removing obsolete data bits from the cover medium (which can be altered without losing the medium integrity). Syndrome, embedding creates a stego medium by substituting certain redundant data bits for the hidden data message. Syndrome Trellis Codes are basically binary linear convolution codes described by the quest for matrix parity. This representation allows it to be used where channel code is not required to troubleshoot data. Therefore steganography is the case.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Reference [1] suggests that Steganography is widely classified on the basis of Spatial-domain and transform-domain. The hidden messages are specifically located within the spatial domain. By changing the cover image's Gabor coefficients the steganography scheme embeds the secret message. The data hiding technique using DWT was executed on both the hidden and the cover images. The secret message can be found in the high frequency coefficients performed on the cover in DWT. Recently the data hiding method has become important in many areas of application.

